

Grafting of Ni(acac)₂ complex on hydroxyapatite support for suitable speciation of Ni and intensification of the CO₂ methanation reaction

Nassima Berroug, Miguel A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz, Juan R. González-Velasco, Zouhair Boukha*

Chemical Technologies for Environmental Sustainability Group, Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, P.O. Box 644, E-48080 Bilbao, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Green hydrogen (GH₂) is considered one of the most promising vectors capable of leading the energy transition, to achieve net-zero carbon emissions, and to reduce reliance on traditional energy raw materials. In this sense, to address the challenging storage and transport issues, its catalytic transformation through reaction with the unavoidable emitted CO₂ for synthetic natural gas (SNG) production appears to be an attractive strategy enabling the implementation of Power-to-Gas technology.

Here we report the high activity of a novel series of active materials composed of Ni(acac)₂ complex grafted on hydroxyapatite (HAP) support in the CO₂ methanation reaction. Optimal grafting conditions were achieved at 30 °C, yielding up to 4.6 % Ni loading (9.6 Ni at. nm⁻²). With reference to previously reported impregnated Ni/HAP samples, the characterization of the activated grafted catalysts shows that the grafting method seems to enhance the reducibility and improve the dispersion of supported Ni species exhibiting smaller average sizes (3.2–6.3 nm). The activated Ni(acac)₂/HAP grafted catalysts demonstrated a promising performance in the CO₂ methanation reaction, shedding light on their suitability and competitiveness when compared with reference materials. The optimized Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) sample exhibits a T₅₀ value close to 313 °C and its maximum conversion (84 %) can be achieved at 400 °C. On the other hand, it is found a clear correlation between turnover frequency (TOF) values and the relative abundance of easily reducible Ni species as well as the most reactive basic sites. Water addition temporarily reduces the activity; however, this effect is reversible since the activity is fully restored upon water removal.

Introduction

The clean energy technologies, based on the use of green hydrogen (GH₂) as a fuel, are expected to play a key role for climate neutrality [1–3]. The current global energy crisis further emphasizes the importance of GH₂ not only for the energy transition, to decrease carbon emissions, but also to reduce dependency on traditional energy raw materials which are exposed to high supply risk. However, numerous challenges seem to delay the application of GH₂ as energy vector at a large-scale. For instance, it is known that various components of natural gas (NG) transmission and distribution networks are incompatible with hydrogen. Consequently, building gigantic hydrogen pipelines and storage sites require important investments and a long timeframe. Thus, this scenario warrants the development of strategies with the aim of taking advantage of the NG storage and transport facilities. In this sense, the re-utilization of the unavoidable emitted CO₂, through its catalytic

reaction with GH₂ for synthetic NG production (CO₂ methanation) is an attractive strategy for implementing Power-to-Gas technology [1–3]. Thus, CO₂ methanation combines the benefits of recycling CO₂, a major greenhouse gas, while also addressing challenging issues related to GH₂ storage and transport.

The CO₂ methanation reaction is thermodynamically favored at low temperatures; therefore, the use of a catalyst is essential to overcome kinetic barriers and enable the reaction under mild temperatures. The efficient catalytic formulations for CO₂ methanation must be able to achieve CO₂ conversions (X_{CO₂}) close to the equilibrium conditions at low temperatures (<450 °C) and the selectivity towards CH₄ formation (S_{CH₄}) should be maximized as much as possible [1–8]. Owing to their promising performances, Ni-based catalysts have attracted an increasing interest, thus becoming promising candidates to provide a viable alternative to noble metals in terms of cost-effectiveness. Nevertheless, they still face several challenges since there are some issues that limit their

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: zouhair.boukha@ehu.eus (Z. Boukha).

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practical use. For instance, due to their low specific activity, compared to Ru catalysts, the Ni catalyst formulations are often prepared through deposition of high Ni loadings. This strategy, however, induces the occurrence of a non-uniform distribution and makes difficult obtaining a major contribution of a highly dispersed species population. This in turns negatively affects the overall activity and lowers the resistance of Ni catalysts under the CO₂ methanation reaction conditions. Moreover, despite their textural and mechanical properties, the traditional supports have shown a number of disadvantages related to the distribution and speciation of Ni [7–10]. For instance, it is known that, when supported on alumina, the calcination of Ni species readily leads to the formation of stable nickel aluminate spinel structures. Consequently, the activation of resulting Ni species, under reducing atmospheres, requires high treatment temperatures (>700 °C), which often provokes agglomeration/loss of their active phases. To overcome such drawbacks, considering the extreme importance of the nature of the used support, several porous materials have been used with the aim of developing suitable interactions with the supported phase and to reduce as much as possible the size of the resulting active species [2,7].

Furthermore, despite a little attention has been paid, the preparation method of the supported active materials is of great importance [9–16]. Therefore, this would mainly affect the nature of metal-support interactions, the size of resulting metallic particles and their resistance to sintering. These parameters have been proved to be key factors influencing their catalytic behavior. For this, several innovative and cost-effective methods have been developed for the performance optimization of supported catalysts by controlling the synthesis procedures and conditions. In most cases, metal particle size has been considered as the chief metric of the synthesis efficacy. Among the effective routes for the immobilization of the metallic supported phase, it is known that grafting of metal complexes is a method that allows obtaining a highly dispersed catalyst with strong metal-support interactions [11]. Covalent immobilization is the most used strategy that allows a strong anchoring of metal complex on the support surface, through forming single or multiple bonds; thus, their coverage mainly depends on the number of hydroxyl groups on the support surface. The metal precursors used typically include acetylacetonates, alkoxides, carbonyls and metal halides. For the synthesis of Ni-grafted catalysts, nickel acetylacetonate (Ni(acac)₂) precursor has been widely used due to its availability and low cost. Moreover, its thermal decomposition requires substantially lower temperatures than inorganic precursors [12]. Babich et al. [14] studied the role of the support nature in the efficiency of Ni(acac)₂ grafting method. Chemical analysis showed that Ni loading was found to be close to 2 Ni at. nm⁻² over silica, whereas it did not exceed 1.3 Ni at. nm⁻² over alumina support. Nevertheless, they demonstrated that, irrespective of the used support, chemisorption of Ni(acac)₂ occurred via a chemical reaction of Ni(acac)₂ with surface hydroxyl groups. Quek et al. [13] compared the catalytic behavior of a series of Ni/SiO₂ catalysts, in DRM, prepared through different methods, namely grafting, direct synthesis and impregnation. The Ni-grafted sample was prepared using Ni(acac)₂ precursor dissolved in toluene. They found that the grafted catalyst exhibited the best performance in terms of activity and stability, which was mainly due to the abundance of highly dispersed Ni species and the nature of the moderate reactivity of surface carbonaceous species. They concluded that, in contrast to the conventional impregnation, the grafting method prevented migration and sintering of metallic active phases and improved markedly strength and stability. Pu et al. [9] deposited Ni nanoparticles (NPs) on nanostructured CeO₂-based supports by using a liquid-phase modification method, starting from Ni(acac)₂ complex as a precursor, for CO₂ methanation reaction. The characterization of the series of Ni-modified ceria nanocrystals evidenced the occurrence of strong metal support interactions (SMSI) with different degrees after their activation with H₂ and/or when submitted to CO₂ hydrogenation reaction conditions. The encapsulated Ni NPs were found to be associated with the abundance of oxygen vacancies, which were essential for the activation of CO₂ at low temperatures. Wen

et al. [10] designed Ni catalyst formulations composed of a commercial SiO₂ impregnated with distinct Ni precursors, namely Ni acetate, Ni nitrate, Ni sulfate, Ni(acac)₂ and Ni chloride. The catalytic activity in the CO₂ methanation results revealed that Ni(acac)₂ was the optimum precursor due to the presence of relatively highly dispersed Ni metallic phase, sized 26 nm, and the occurrence of strong interactions metal-support. However, their long-term stability test showed a decay in the activity of the optimized Ni(acac)₂/SiO₂ catalyst within 10 h time-on-stream (TOS), since the CO₂ conversion significantly decreased from 62 to 46 %.

Despite its promising potential, the application of HAP as a catalyst support for the CO₂ methanation reaction has few precedents in the literature [1,2,17–19]. According to our previous reports, adopting a simple impregnation method for Ni deposition on HAP results in a highly performant free-promoter formulation [1,2]. For this reason, studies aimed at investigating strategies for the improvement of the reported achievements are lacking to make a rational use of these materials. In line with this, in the present study, a series of Ni(acac)₂ complex grafted on HAP is prepared, characterized and assayed in the CO₂ methanation reaction. It is worthy to notice that the immobilization of Ni over HAP support through grafting method, for the decarbonization processes, has not been yet investigated.

Materials and methods

Synthesis of the catalyst formulation

Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (>9 %), (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (≥98 %) and Ni(C₅H₇O₂)₂ (Ni(acac)₂ (95 %), Lot: MKCJ9587) salts used in this study were purchased from Merck.

The synthesis of HAP support, to obtain a stoichiometric composition, was carried out through a modified version of the co-precipitation method [1,2,20,21]. Typically, this consists on mixing two solutions composed of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (235.6 g L⁻¹) and (NH₄)₂HPO₄ (78.85 g L⁻¹) salts. The white suspension was completely dissolved in a nitric acid solution (1.3 mol L⁻¹) and then, added drop wise to ammonia solution (4.7 mol L⁻¹) to reach a pH of 10. The precipitate was heated up to 85 °C, under vigorous stirring, and maintained at this temperature for 16 h. Then, the recovered solid was (i) filtered, (ii) washed, (iii) dried at 120 °C for 12 h and (iv) finally calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

The Ni-modified HAP samples were synthesized through grafting method by using toluene as a solvent [22,23]. First, Ni(acac)₂ precursor was dissolved in toluene at 60 °C. Thereafter, the dissolution temperature was adjusted to the desired value and then, 3 g of HAP support was added, under vigorous stirring. The suspension was kept in isothermal conditions for a determined time interval. It was then vacuum-filtered and washed with pure toluene. The obtained grafted solid was dried at 80 °C for 12 h; and it was finally calcined at 500 °C (5 °C min⁻¹, for 4 h). Table 1 summarizes the different conditions used for the preparation of the grafted samples. Note that a number of parameters have been studied, namely temperature, grafting time and initial precursor concentration, respectively.

Methods and techniques for characterization of the grafted catalysts

The actual amounts of Ni in the grafted catalysts were determined by wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF). The analyses were

Table 1

Grafting conditions used for the optimization of the deposition of Ni(acac)₂ precursor on the HAP support.

Parameter studied	T, °C	Time, h	[Ni(acac) ₂], g L ⁻¹
Grafting temperature	30–75	6	2.6
Grafting time	30	1–5	2.6
Precursor initial concentration	30	3	2.6–7.8

conducted using a PANalytical AXIOS spectrometer.

In order to study the decomposition process of the Ni(acac)₂ precursor adsorbed on as-prepared samples, they were submitted to thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), under oxidizing conditions (5 % O₂/N₂). The experiments were carried out on a TGA 550 DISCOVERY series at atmospheric pressure. For their analysis, the samples were (i) stabilized at 80 °C for 1 h, (ii) heated to 500 °C (5 °C min⁻¹), (iii) hold for 4 h at 500 °C and (iv) finally heated to 1000 °C (5 °C min⁻¹).

Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) technique was applied to examine the oxidation state and the evolution of the optical properties of Ni species and their interaction with the HAP support. The analyses were performed on a Cary 5000 apparatus within a range of 200–2200 nm.

The N₂ physisorption studies were carried out on a TRISTAR II 3020 equipment. The samples were pretreated under N₂ flow at 300 °C, for 6 h. The specific surface areas were measured according to Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method.

The temperature-programmed reduction with H₂ (H₂-TPR) experiments were conducted on an AutoChem 2920 apparatus, equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). First, the samples were cleaned in a flow of 5 % O₂/He at 500 °C (10 °C min⁻¹, for 30 min) and, then, cooled to 100 °C in Ar. The H₂-TPR diagrams were recorded operating under a 5 % H₂/Ar flow, 50 cm³ min⁻¹, in the temperature interval ranging between 100 and 600 °C (10 °C min⁻¹). The produced water was condensed in a cold trap by using a mixture of isopropyl alcohol and liquid nitrogen.

The morphology, dispersion and Ni particle sizes spread on the activated samples have been investigated by using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) techniques. Prior to the measurements, the samples were sonicated in ethanol for 2 min. The images were taken with a high resolution Tecnai F30 microscope (FEI company), working at 300 kV. The High Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) images were taken with a Fischione detector. In parallel, the surface chemical composition was extracted from X-ray energy dispersive spectra (EDS) obtained with an EDAX detector.

The macro-structural studies on the reduced catalysts were conducted by using X-ray diffraction (XRD) techniques. The analyses were performed on a X'PERT-MPD X-ray diffractometer (anticathode Cu K α) at room temperature. The degree of inconsistency (χ_i), between XRD and HAADF results, was calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$\chi_i = \frac{|d_{XRD} - d_{HAADF}|}{d_{XRD}} \quad (1)$$

where d_{XRD} and d_{HAADF} are the average diameters of Ni NPs estimated from HAADF and XRD results, respectively.

The analyses of the near surface of the reduced catalysts were carried out by using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) techniques. The analyses were performed with the help of a SPECS PHOIBOS 150 1D-DLD spectrometer. For the charge shift correction, the C 1s feature was used as a reference (peak at 284.6 eV). CASA XPS software was used for the deconvolution of the main peaks for Ni 2p, Ca 2p, P 2p, O 1s and C 1s regions. Prior to their analysis the samples were activated under a reducing atmosphere (20 % H₂/Ar) at 500 °C, for 1 h, in a special cell (HT SPECS), allowing working at high temperatures.

The surface basic properties of the activated samples were investigated by using temperature programmed desorption of CO₂ (CO₂-TPD). The analysis device consisted on a mass spectrometer (Hidden Analytical). First, the samples (100 mg) were activated in a flow of 5 % H₂/Ar (50 cm³ min⁻¹) at 500 °C for 1 h. Thereafter, they were (i) cooled in He to 50 °C, (ii) submitted to a flow of 1 % CO₂/He for 30 min and (iii) finally, the CO₂ desorption step involved flowing He at 50 °C for 1 h, followed by a heat treatment up to 800 °C with a ramp of 10 °C min⁻¹.

Moreover, studies concerned with the temperature programmed surface reaction (TPSR) were performed using the same experimental device used for TPD experiments. In this case the activated sample was

(i) submitted to a 1 % CO₂/He flow at 100 °C (30 min), (ii) switched to a 5 % H₂/Ar flow, (iii) hold at 100 °C for 30 min, and finally (iv) heated to 800 °C with a ramp of 10 °C min⁻¹.

Catalysis experiments

The performance of the Ni-grafted catalysts in the CO₂ methanation reaction was studied by using a SS tubular reactor (Ref. CNLX99012-316, ID = 9 mm) under atmospheric pressure. To facilitate heat dissipation, the catalysts (500 mg, 160–250 μ m) were diluted with quartz sand to obtain a bed volume of 1.5 cm³. First, the catalysts were activated in a 20 % H₂/N₂ flow at 500 °C (1 h) and, then, cooled down to 200 °C in a flow of N₂. Thereafter, the samples were submitted to the reaction gas mixture, composed of CO₂/H₂/N₂ (1/4/1.25), with a total flow rate equal to 250 cm³ min⁻¹.

The reactants and products of the reaction were analyzed by using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890B) equipped with a TCD detector. The values of X_{CO₂}, S_{CH₄} and S_{CO} were estimated by using the input (F_i^{in}) and output (F_i^{out}) molar flows, respectively, according to the following equations [1,2]:

$$X_{CO_2} = \frac{F_{CO_2}^{in} - F_{CO_2}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S_{CH_4} = \frac{F_{CH_4}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in} - F_{CO_2}^{out}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$S_{CO} = \frac{F_{CO}^{out}}{F_{CO_2}^{in} - F_{CO_2}^{out}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

The reaction rate and turnover frequency (TOF) values were estimated operating under differential reactor conditions. For this, additional experiments were conducted in a temperature interval of 250–350 °C, using smaller amounts of the catalysts (50–100 mg), to obtain low CO₂ conversion values ($\leq 10\%$).

Results and discussion

Optimization of grafting conditions

Effect of the temperature

Fig. 1 reports the results of the optimization study performed to determine the experimental conditions suitable to achieve a high efficacy in the grafting process of Ni(acac)₂ on the HAP support. According to Fig. 1a, the grafting yield is highly dependent on the preparation temperature ranging between 30–75 °C. At 30 °C, the total amounts of Ni species dissolved in toluene are adsorbed/retained on the solid, which corresponds to an efficacy close to 100 % and a surface density close to 3.9 Ni at. nm⁻². However, raising the mixtures temperature induces a systematic decrease in the grafting capacity, which does not exceed 52 % (2 Ni at. nm⁻²) at 75 °C. This reduction in adsorption affinity with increasing the temperature can be explained by a change in the thermodynamic equilibrium parameters. Instead, this evolution would imply a loss in the number of specific adsorption sites, most likely associated with those hosting physisorbed complex species. By contrast, the remaining Ni(acac)₂ adsorbed fraction is rather attached to the surface by chemical bonds [14,23]. It is also worthy to notice that the surface density reached at 75 °C (2 Ni at. nm⁻²) agrees with that reported by Babich et al. [14], in their study on the chemisorption of Ni(acac)₂ on the surface of silica, performed at elevated temperature (220 °C).

Effect of the grafting time

Fig. 1b shows the dependence of the grafting yield on the time of Ni(acac)₂ adsorption on the HAP surface. In this case, different time intervals have been applied for a salt solution presenting an initial

Fig. 1. Study on the parameters affecting the grafting efficacy of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ complex on the HAP support ($W_{\text{HAP}} = 3 \text{ g}$). Effect of (a) grafting temperature, (b) grafting time and (c) precursor initial concentration. Selected experimental conditions were repeated up to three times to verify reproducibility, with a margin of error of approximately 2 %.

concentration of 2.6 g L^{-1} . The adsorption process of the complex molecules is characterized by a rapid increase in the Ni retained amounts during the first 30 min, followed by a period of stabilization to reach the equilibrium state conditions. The obtained results also evidence that the amounts of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ dissolved in toluene can be adsorbed completely within the two first hours. Considering the relatively short time required for the saturation of the support surface, it can be concluded that the complex molecules easily diffuse through the pores of the HAP supports [23].

Effect of the initial concentration

Fig. 1c illustrates the impact of the initial concentration of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ precursor on the grafting efficacy. For this study, 3 g of HAP powder was immersed in toluene solutions with different concentrations of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$. Working with small contents ($\leq 2.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) results in a total retention of the Ni precursor. As expected, due to the surface saturation effect, the progressive addition of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ induces a systematic decrease of the grafting yield, from 100 %, for a concentration of 2.6 g L^{-1} , to 88 %, starting with a concentration of 7.8 g L^{-1} . In parallel, it appears that the $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ adsorption process on the HAP support results in Ni loadings exhibiting an upper limit close to 4.6 %. This corresponds to a surface density close to $9.6 \text{ Ni at. nm}^{-2}$, which is significantly smaller than that expected for a theoretical monolayer ($20.7 \text{ Ni at. nm}^{-2}$). This result is in reasonable agreement with the difference in the size of the complex when compared with Ni atoms and/or the number of the available surface sites (reactive hydroxyl groups) lying on the support [14,27,28].

Characterization of as-grafted samples

Previous reports claimed that the interaction complex-surface mainly depends on the nature of surface sites [23–27]. In most cases, with independence of the used support, this interaction involves surface hydroxyl groups. To provide insight into the sites involved, TGA analyses were performed on the as-prepared grafted samples to follow the decomposition of the adsorbed complex species under oxidizing atmospheres. As expected, in agreement with the data reported in Fig. 1a, the TGA diagrams (Fig. S1) show that the % of weight loss observed at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ depends on the grafting temperature. Moreover, the DTG profiles reported in Fig. 2a show that the peaks for the supported samples are shifted towards lower temperatures, when compared with that of pure $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$, indicating that the decomposition of the complex is somewhat facilitated when it is adsorbed on the support surface. Interestingly, all grafted samples show a positive peak occurring around $380\text{--}390 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; probably due to the formation of NiO species [29]. Taking into account this oxidation process together with the decomposition of the organic matter, composed of two acac ligands, the observed total weight loss values at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ are very close to those expected theoretically. For instance, the sample T-30 exhibits a weight loss of 6.4 %, which is consistent with a theoretical value equal to 6.6 %. Moreover, DTG diagram for this sample exhibits two main peaks, centered at 186 and $295 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, attesting to the decomposition of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ derived species attached to at least two different sites (Fig. 2a). However, the profiles of the samples grafted at higher temperatures ($40\text{--}75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) exhibit only one main peak centered at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ together with a much less intense feature at $125 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, due to adsorbed water; whilst the feature peaked at $186 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ completely disappears. This suggests that increasing the anchoring temperature provokes a loss in specific surface sites prone to host complex derived species [23]. Womes et al. [23] proposed that the grafting process of $\text{Pt}(\text{acac})_2$ on alumina may involve two different sites, classified according to their complex-support interaction strength: (i) physisorption occurred on deactivated surface composed of A sites, whereas (ii) a stronger adsorption took place on the reactive surface through chemisorption on B sites. Accordingly, it is clear that, with independence of the preparation temperature, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ strongly chemisorbs on the sites decomposing at relatively elevated temperatures; however, the sites available for physisorption retain the $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ complex at the lowest temperature only ($30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Similar interpretations can be found in previous studies dealing with the deposition of $\text{Pt}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2$ complexes, respectively, on porous materials [23–27].

DRS technique was used to study the evolution of the optical properties of Ni species and their interactions with the HAP support, for the samples grafted at different temperatures ($30\text{--}75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and dried at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 2b and 2c). In order to be used as references the spectra of the bare support and a mechanical mixture (HAP + $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$) are displayed as well. The UV–Vis spectrum of the support shows an intense band, at 210

Fig. 2. (a) DTG diagrams under 5 %O₂/N₂ flow (50 cm³ g⁻¹), (b) UV–Visible and (c) NIR spectra for as-grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP samples at 30, 40, 50, 60 and 75 °C (namely Ni-T30, Ni-T40, Ni-T50, Ni-T60 and Ni-T75, respectively).

nm, assigned to O²⁻ → Ca²⁺ charge transfers (Fig. 2b) [30]. In addition, according to Fig. 2c, the support also exhibits two features in the NIR interval, centered at 1385 and 1430 nm, attributed to hydroxyl groups [30]. The mechanical mixture (HAP + Ni(acac)₂) shows several bands attributed to Ni²⁺ ions. In the UV region an intense absorption band is observed at 296 nm, associated with O²⁻ → Ni²⁺ charge transfers. In the visible domain there are several bands due to different coordination of Ni²⁺. The two shoulders centered at 380 and 750 nm, respectively, can be assigned to ν₃ (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(P)) and ν₂ (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}) d-d transitions in an octahedral (Oh) symmetry [30]; whereas the band peaked at 640 nm is attributed to tetrahedrally (Td) coordinated Ni²⁺ species [51]. Moreover, according to Fig. 2c, there is a broad band due to ν₁ (³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F)) transition, located in the NIR domain, which tends to split in two bands centered at 1060 and 1180 nm [30].

Interestingly, when compared with the spectrum of pure HAP, the NIR spectra for the grafted samples show that the bands due to OH groups (1385 and 1430 nm) are significantly less intense. This result demonstrates that Ni(acac)₂ complex interacts with surface OH groups. Likewise, except for the feature linked to O²⁻ → Ni²⁺ charge transfers, the grafted samples exhibit the characteristic Ni²⁺ bands with very low intensity. Moreover, these features systematically redshift with increasing the grafting temperature, suggesting a progressive evolution in the optical properties of Ni²⁺ ions; especially, it is worthy to notice the disappearance of the band due to tetrahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ species (640 nm), for the samples grafted at T ≥ 40 °C. In line with the occurrence of complex-support interactions, these observations point out that when grafted at 30 °C the Ni species are distributed between two hosting sites (Td and Oh). However, at higher grafting temperatures Ni²⁺ ions preferentially occupy octahedral coordination. Thus, in agreement with the DTG results, it can be concluded that physisorbed Ni(acac)₂ derived species comprise tetrahedral Ni²⁺ sites, whilst chemisorption of Ni(acac)₂ complex would mainly lead to a dominant phase composed of octahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ species.

Characterization of the activated catalysts

Once the optimization study on the grafting conditions of the Ni(acac)₂ precursor on the HAP support is concluded, in the following we will continue with the examination of the properties and the performance of a selected series of catalysts, grafted at 30 °C, and calcined at 500 °C. This approach is adopted, because it offers the possibility to

probe a large interval of Ni loadings (up to 4.6 wt%). Note that, for their activation, the resulting Ni(acac)₂/HAP samples have been reduced under a flow of 20 % H₂/Ar at 500 °C.

Textural properties

Fig. S2 and Fig. S3 (Supporting Information) display the N₂ physisorption isotherms and pore size distribution curves, respectively, for all grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts. The shape of the resulting isotherms show a striking similarity with that of pure HAP (Fig. S2). All of them are identical to type IV isotherms (IUPAC) given by mesoporous materials. Furthermore, according to Fig. S3, the pore sizes for all samples present a unimodal distribution, presenting maxima around 35–39 nm. Table 2 summarizes the textural parameters of the grafted samples estimated through the analysis of their isotherms. With reference to pure HAP (51 m² g⁻¹), it can be observed that the addition of Ni induces a smooth loss in the BET specific surface area (S_{BET}). In parallel, the average pore diameter also shows a slight decrease in the Ni-modified samples. These results indicate that the grafting process does not influence significantly the textural properties of the used support.

Reducibility of the grafted catalysts

H₂-TPR studies were carried out in order to explore the reduction properties of the Ni-grafted catalysts (Fig. 3). Note that the bare support does not show any reduction peak (Fig. S4), indicating that all peaks observed correspond to the reduction of Ni species. The profiles for all grafted samples show two main reduction features at temperatures lower than 500 °C, which can be attributed to the reduction of at least two Ni phases exhibiting different nature. Note that, except for Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(3) catalyst, the profiles also exhibit a shoulder, occurring in the range of 200–260 °C, which can be associated with the reduction of Ni₂O₃ phase (α species). A similar feature was found in other Ni-based systems like Ni/Al₂O₃ [31] and Ni/Nb₂O₅ [32]. According to Table 2, the contribution of this α phase represents the 3.8 %, 9.6 % and 15.1 % of the total reducible species on Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(2), Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(4) and Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) samples, respectively. It is worth mentioning that these unusual species were not observed in our previous reports dealing with Ni/HAP impregnated samples [1,2], which suggests vital influence of the preparation procedures on the speciation of supported Ni phases. At higher temperatures, the diagrams exhibit two main reduction domains. The first one, peaked at 285–325 °C, can be assigned to easily reducible surface NiO species (type β), while the second feature

Table 2
WDXRF, BET, HAADF, XRD and H₂-TPR data for the grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts.

Catalysts	WDXRF Ni, %	BET S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _p , nm	HAADF d _{Ni} , nm	D, %	XRD d _{Ni} , nm	Ni lattice micro- strain	Reducibility, μmol _{H2} g ⁻¹			
									Total	α species	β species	γ species
HAP	0	51	0.39	27.7	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(2)	1.9	52	0.35	24.7	3.2 ± 0.7	30.6	24.8	-0.0246	328	12.4 (3.8 %)	133.7	181.9 (56 %)
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(3)	2.9	49	0.38	28.9	5.4 ± 1.5	19.0	14.2	-0.0103	480	0	231.0	249.0 (52 %)
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(4)	3.6	48	0.36	27.3	6.3 ± 2.4	16.0	10.1	-0.0053	630	60.7 (9.6 %)	407.9	161.5 (26 %)
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(5)	4.6	49	0.36	26.4	6.3 ± 2.1	15.2	10.6	-0.0057	780	118.1 (15.1 %)	422.2	239.7 (30 %)

(450–485 °C) may correspond to hardly reducible species (type γ), probably located in the bulk of larger NiO particles [1,2]. In fact, though moderate, the progressive addition of Ni systematically shifts the observed peaks towards high temperatures, which actually attests to a growth of the NiO phase particles. In parallel, this leads to a large contribution of the easily reducible NiO species (type β).

Morphology and distribution of Ni particle sizes

Fig. 4 illustrates the HAADF images for the activated grafted catalysts and Ni particle size distribution, derived from their statistical analysis. Likewise, the estimated values corresponding to the mean Ni particle sizes and their dispersion are listed in Table 2. In general, the Ni particles exhibit a quasi-spherical shape. However, their distribution depends on the concentration of Ni deposits. The Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(2) grafted sample shows the smallest Ni NPs (3.2 nm) and a narrow distribution. The progressive addition of Ni, however, seems to induce a systematic growth of its particles, becoming significantly larger and exhibiting a broader distribution. Thus, the catalysts bearing a high concentration of loaded Ni (Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(4) and Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5)) comprise the biggest particles, showing a size close to 6.3 nm. Nevertheless, it is worth outlining that the range of average sizes estimated on the Ni grafted catalysts (3.2–6.3 nm) are significantly smaller than those measured on Ni/HAP impregnated sample (13.9 nm), reported in our previous studies [1,2]. With reference to the impregnation method, the grafting method adopted in the present work actually represents an important advance, leading to an improvement of Ni dispersion on the HAP support.

Macrostructure of the activated Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts

The structural properties of the Ni grafted catalysts, activated under reducing atmosphere at 500 °C, have been investigated by means of XRD techniques (Fig. 5a). The patterns of the bare support shows a striking similarity to those of hydroxyapatite reference materials, presenting an hexagonal crystal system (JCPDS: 01-082-256) and belonging to P6₃/m symmetry (space group n° 176). The diffractograms of Ni-modified samples show the presence of metallic Ni as a unique derived crystalline phase (JCPDS: 89-7120), which evidences a complete reduction of Ni species. Interestingly, no significant effect of Ni grafting process on the position of the peaks of HAP support can be noticed; indicating that this does not induce profound changes in its lattice properties.

For the estimation of the mean size of Ni particles, Scherrer equation has been applied by using the most intense peak of Ni⁰ (111), centered around 44.5° (Fig. 5b). Unexpectedly, as it can be deduced from the corresponding data listed in Table 2, the progressive addition of Ni leads to a decrease of Ni crystallite size (from 24.8 nm, for Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(2), to 14.2 nm, for Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(3) and 10.3 ± 0.3 nm, for Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(4) and Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5)). It should be outlined that this general trend contrasts with that given by HAADF techniques. Previous reports associated this difference with the occurrence of Ni lattice imperfections leading to strain broadening effects. In concrete, these factors may influence the broadening of the diffraction peak and provide misleading values of the crystallite size. To evaluate this possibility, an

approximation method to estimate micro-strain (ε) values in the Ni crystallites has been used [33–35]. For all grafted samples, this parameter estimated according to Williamson Hall procedures, Fig. S5, exhibits negative values, which suggests the occurrence of compressive strain (ε < 0) rather than tensile strain effect (ε > 0) [33]. Fig. 5c displays the dependence of the absolute values of Ni lattice micro-strain and the degree of inconsistency between HAADF and XRD techniques on the Ni loading. It can be observed that both parameters evolve following a similar trend. Moreover, in line with a decrease in the relative abundance of metal-support interfacial sites, this compressive strain generally decreases with the Ni loading increase.

Surface analysis of the grafted samples

The distribution of the different species spread on the grafted catalysts surface was investigated by means of XPS techniques. It should be noted that the samples were pretreated in-situ under reducing conditions (20 % H₂/Ar) at 500 °C for 1 h. Data obtained from the analysis of collected spectra are summarized in Table 3 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 6a displays the XPS spectra corresponding to Ca 2p region for the activated catalysts. All analyzed samples show two typical main peaks, centered at 347 ± 0.1 eV (Ca 2p_{3/2}) and 350.6 ± 0.1 eV (Ca 2p_{1/2}), attributed to Ca²⁺ species located in the HAP framework [36,37]. In this sense, it is known that in the HAP lattice Ca²⁺ ions occupy two distinct sites: Ca(I) and Ca(II). The first type, representing 40 % of the total Ca²⁺ species, is surrounded by phosphate groups and forms nine Ca-O bonds, while the second one (60 %) forms channels that host OH⁻ ions. Note that the latter (Ca(II)) are more prone to be exchanged with a variety of cationic species. Previous reports associated the Ca 2p_{1/2} BEs with Ca(I) sites whereas the Ca 2p_{3/2} feature was linked to the total Ca²⁺ species in the HAP structure [36,37]. On the basis of the integration of Ca 2p_{1/2} and Ca 2p_{3/2} peaks, the relative amounts of the Ca(I) sites were found to be around 38–42 % for all analyzed samples, which is close to that corresponding to a standard HAP structure (40 %). In turn, this result would imply that in the Ni-modified samples, the Ca²⁺ species are less likely exchanged with supported Ni²⁺ species.

Likewise, though not displayed, the spectra recorded in the P 2p region show that the addition of Ni does not induce a significant change in the position of the phosphorus characteristic peaks. In accordance with Table 3, all spectra exhibit a typical feature at 133.5 ± 0.1 eV assigned to P-O bonds of the phosphate groups present in the HAP structure [1,2].

The O 1s spectra for the Ni-modified samples are shown in Fig. 6b. The deconvolution of the main reveals that it is likely composed of two components peaked at 530.7 ± 0.1 eV and 529.6 ± 0.5 eV. According to the literature data, these features could be assigned to O-P and O-Ca bonds, respectively, in the HAP lattice [36].

Fig. 6c presents the XPS spectra in the Ni 2p region (Ni 2p_{3/2} and Ni 2p_{1/2} doublet). To identify the contribution of each phase the deconvolution of the resulting spectra was made by maintaining an equal spin-orbit splitting (17.2 eV) and a constant Ni 2p_{3/2} to Ni 2p_{1/2} area ratio (~2). According to the XPS data listed in Table 3, all spectra exhibit

Fig. 3. H₂-TPR profiles for the calcined Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts.

a main Ni 2p_{3/2} feature peaked at 852.4 eV and a shake-up satellite peak at 857.9 ± 0.2 eV. In agreement with XRD and H₂-TPR results, these values point out that the activated samples mainly comprise a metallic Ni phase [1,2,38]. This result sheds light on the suitability of HAP support for Ni catalysts. Interestingly, the analyzed samples show differences in the broadness of their Ni 3p_{3/2} peaks. This suggests that the progressive addition of Ni induces a change in the nature and/or the abundance of the surrounding species. The corresponding FWHM values, reported in Table 3, show that the samples with low Ni loadings exhibit a relatively much broader peak (2.74–2.88 eV) when compared with those bearing large amounts of Ni (2.25–2.27 eV), indicating that in the latter the Ni environment presents a relatively higher homogeneity. We assume that this trend is most likely linked to an evolution in the strength of metal-support interactions, probably weaker in the case of Ni-rich samples.

Surface chemistry and reactivity of the grafted catalysts

The surface basicity of the grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP samples was investigated by using CO₂-TPD techniques (Fig. 7). The diagram of the bare support shows two CO₂ desorption features. The first domain occurring at relatively low temperatures (<500 °C) is associated with weak basic sites, whereas the thermally stable sites (strong basic sites) decompose at higher temperatures (>500 °C). Upon integration of the resulting peaks the density of basic sites is found to be around 80 μmol_{CO2} g⁻¹ (Table 4). A comparison with literature data shows that the surface basicity of HAP (0.95 molec. CO₂ nm⁻²) is more than three times larger than that of alumina (0.3 molec. CO₂ nm⁻²), reported herein [39], which actually makes of HAP materials such interesting basic carriers. Interestingly, as deduced from the data reported in Table 4, the addition of Ni onto HAP dramatically influences its surface basic properties. On the one hand, this increases the total number of basic sites; on the other hand, it significantly affects their distribution, since on the Ni-modified samples there is a larger density of weak basic sites (77–99 μmol_{CO2} g⁻¹) compared with that measured on the bare support (45.6 μmol_{CO2} g⁻¹).

In order to examine the reactivity of the basic sites in the grafted samples, TPSR experiments in H₂ stream have been carried out with pre-adsorbed CO₂. Fig. 7b reports the recorded diagrams accounting for the evolution of CH₄ signal versus the temperature. The analyzed samples exhibit a main peak centered in the range 204–227 °C, a less intense one peaked around 400 °C and a third feature, thermally stable, occurring at high temperatures (>500 °C). This indicates that the hydrogenation of the retained CO₂ involves at least three different active basic sites. According to Table 4, the total density values of the resulting reactive sites, estimated by integration of the TPSR peaks, are found to be ranging between 31.7–40 μmol_{CH4} g⁻¹. Furthermore, the contribution of the fraction needing a high temperature for hydrogenation seems to depend on the analyzed sample; while the Ni(acac)₂-HAP-(3) presents the largest fraction (14.9 %), the Ni(acac)₂-HAP-(5) bears the smallest fraction (7.8 %) of these thermally stable basic sites. It should be highlighted that this general trend is consistent with the abundance of α reducible species detected on the H₂-TPR diagrams. It can be concluded that the presence of these specific reducible species promotes the reactivity of the basic sites, most likely located close to each other.

Catalytic performance

Fig. 8a and Fig. 8b show the light-off plots for the CO₂ methanation reaction obtained over the Ni(acac)₂/HAP grafted catalysts. For the sake of comparison, the activity of an optimized impregnated Ni sample (Ni/HAP-imp), reported in our previous study [2], is also included. On the Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(2) sample the activity begins at 225 °C; thereafter, the CO₂ conversion increases with the temperature to reach a value close to 50 % (T₅₀) at 375 °C and achieves that of the thermodynamic equilibrium (78 %) at T_{max} close to 450 °C (Fig. 8a). Though moderate, the addition of 3 % Ni seems to decrease smoothly the activity, since the conversion does not approach its maximum value before 475 °C. This

Fig. 4. HAADF images for the activated Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts and the corresponding histogram of Ni particle size distribution.

Fig. 5. (a) XRD patterns for the reduced Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts, (b) zoom in the diffraction angle 2θ of 43–46° and (c) dependence of Ni lattice micro-strain and degree of inconsistency on Ni loading.

Table 3

XPS data for the grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts, reduced at 500 °C.

Sample	Ni 2p _{3/2} , eV	FWHM	Sat 2p _{3/2} , eV	O 1 s, eV	Ca 2p _{3/2} , eV	P 2p, eV	Ca/P	Ni/P	Ni/Ca	O/P
HAP	–	–	–	530.5	346.9	133.6	1.51	0	0	3.6
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(2)	852.4	2.74	857.8	530.6	347.1	133.5	1.57	0.065	0.041	3.6
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(3)	852.4	2.88	858.1	530.8	347.1	133.5	1.53	0.055	0.036	3.5
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(4)	852.4	2.25	857.7	530.6	347.1	133.4	1.55	0.065	0.042	3.5
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(5)	852.4	2.27	857.8	530.6	347.1	133.4	1.52	0.091	0.060	3.3

unexpected behavior of Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(3) can be associated with its peculiar chemical properties. It should be noted that, in contrast to the rest of grafted samples, this catalyst does not comprise easily reducible

Ni species; in parallel, it contains the largest fraction of hardly reactive basic sites. However, bearing larger amounts of grafted Ni implies a systematic improvement of the activity. Thus, among all grafted

Fig. 6. XPS spectra for the activated Ni(acac)₂/HAP samples recorded in (a) Ca 2p (b) O 1s and (c) Ni 2p regions.

catalysts, the Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) sample displays the best catalytic performance, since it exhibits the lowest values of T_{50} and T_{max} (313 °C and 400 °C, respectively). Moreover, as deduced from Fig. 8b, over the whole temperature interval investigated, this grafted catalyst also gives the highest values of selectivity towards methane production; particularly, it achieves a S_{CH_4} value close to 100 % at 400 °C. It is worth noting that all grafted catalysts clearly outperform the optimized catalyst prepared by impregnation method (Ni/HAP-imp), in terms of activity and selectivity. Of course, the grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts comprise smaller Ni NPs (3.2–6.3 nm) compared with those spread on the impregnated sample, 13.9 nm, shown in our previous report. Thus, it can be concluded that the method adopted for the preparation of Ni/HAP samples markedly influences their activity in the CO₂ methanation reaction. The grafting method seems to lead to a suitable distribution of Ni species, consisting of smaller particles, when compared with the impregnation method.

In order to give insight into the importance of the present achievements, we also compare in Fig. 9 the light-off temperature (T_{50}) of our optimized Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) catalyst with those of Ni catalyst formulations reported in previous studies in the literature [1,2,40–45]. Note that, being close to our experimental conditions, only formulations tested under a WHSV ranging between 20,000–55,000 cm³ h⁻¹ g⁻¹ are

presented. When compared with free promoter Ni catalysts (Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/SiO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/ β -zeolite), our grafted sample is found to be, by far, the most active one. To a lesser extent, it is also advantageously competitive to even those containing a promoter phase (Ni/La/Al₂O₃ and Ni/La/ β -zeolite) [40,43]. Despite its moderate textural properties, it seems that the immobilization of Ni active phase on the HAP support, by using the grafting method, confers to our optimized sample much more improved properties, suitable for the CO₂ methanation reaction. The HAP support probably makes the difference because of its peculiar surface chemistry. For instance, the Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) bears a larger density of surface basic sites (2.67 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$) compared with those measured on Ni/Al₂O₃ (0.4 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$) and Ni/SiO₂ (1.5 $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{m}^{-2}$) systems [41,50]. Likewise, the oxidation state of Ni species is also considered as a critical parameter, which deeply influences the performance of the catalytic formulation in the CO₂ methanation reaction. Our XRD, XPS and TPR data point out that the pre-treatment used for the activation of the grafted sample, at 500 °C, leads to a complete reduction of Ni species into Ni⁰ metallic phase. By contrast, this is not the case of Ni/Al₂O₃ and Ni/SiO₂ formulations over which the degree of Ni species reduction did not exceed 56 %, at 500 °C, and 72 %, at 550 °C, respectively [41,45].

Fig. 10a reports the turnover frequency (TOF_{CH₄}) values

Fig. 7. (a) CO₂-TPD and (b) TPSR diagrams for the reduced Ni(acac)₂/HAP grafted catalysts.

Table 4

CO₂-TPD, TPSR and CO₂ methanation activity data for the grafted Ni(acac)₂/HAP catalysts.

Catalysts	CO ₂ -TPD			TPSR		Catalytic activity		
	Basicity, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{g}^{-1}$			CH ₄ formation, $\mu\text{mol}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{g}^{-1}$	CO ₂ methanation		E _a , kJ mol ⁻¹	
	Total	Weak	Strong	Total	T > 500 °C	T ₅₀ , °C		T _{max} , °C
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(2)	137	99	38	40	5.1 (12.7 %)	373	450	83.2
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(3)	110	77	33	38.9	5.8 (14.9 %)	380	475	85.2
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(4)	119	78	40	31.7	3.5 (11 %)	330	425	87.5
Ni(acac) ₂ /HAP-(5)	131	84	47	33.1	2.6 (7.8 %)	313	400	86.3

(250–350 °C), estimated over the grafted catalysts, under differential reactor conditions, estimated as the number of produced CH₄ molecules per surface Ni atoms. Prior to their testing, the catalysts were aged under the reaction mixtures at 500 °C for 12 h. The general trend is consistent with that observed in light-off curves, since the Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) sample maintains a clear superiority. In agreement with a previous study dealing with the metal particle size effect [47,48], this means that, in the range of 3.2–6.3 nm, the use of relatively larger particles (~6.3 nm) is beneficial for the methanation activity. According to Zhu et al. [48] larger particles are rather more active because of their enhanced conduction properties; this, in turn, promotes the formation of methane precursors like HCOO* species. It should be highlighted that the TOF_{CH₄} value measured at 300 °C over our optimized Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) catalyst (0.12 s⁻¹) is close to those estimated on Ni/TiO₂ and Ni/ZrCe catalysts, whilst it is five times larger than that found on a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst, reported by González-Rangulan et al. [46].

The activation energy (E_a) values have been estimated from the Arrhenius plots (Fig. 10b). As can be deduced from the data of Table 4, the E_a values range between 83.2–87.5 kJ mol⁻¹, in good agreement with those estimated over other unpromoted Ni catalysts like Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/TiO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ [43,46]. Note that the prevalent mechanisms for the CO₂ methanation reaction are typically described according to two different schemes: associative and dissociative pathways [49]. The associative mechanism involves an associative adsorption of CO₂ which readily reacts with adsorbed hydrogen to form oxygenate intermediate species, followed by hydrogenation step to produce methane. By contrast, through a dissociative pathway, the adsorbed CO₂ dissociates

into carbonyl and oxygen atom and then CO methanation takes place. However, there is a wide consensus on the fact that both mechanism pathways involve metallic active centers for the activation of H₂ as well as surface basic sites for CO₂ adsorption and activation.

Fig. 10c displays the dependence of TOF_{CH₄} values on the density of reactive strong basic sites. It should be noted that, according to the TPSR data, the hydrogenation of these sites occurs at relatively high temperatures (>500 °C). Interestingly, the correlation curve reveals a systematic decrease of TOF_{CH₄} with the abundance of these specific sites. This suggests that a distribution consisting of a large contribution of strongly chemisorbed CO₂ on thermally stable basic sites actually limits their participation in the reaction at low temperatures and, consequently, this negatively impacts the efficiency of the active sites.

Likewise, Fig. 10d indicates a correlation between the specific activity and the density of the surface reducible active sites (α species), detected in H₂-TPR diagrams. Therefore, the occurrence of this easily reducible fraction may be associated with Ni atoms exposed at the catalyst surface, which are probably more accessible to the reactants.

The stability test performed over the optimal Ni(acac)₂/HAP-(5) sample at 325 °C reveals its high resistance to deactivation during 110 h reaction (Fig. 11). Interestingly, our catalyst is found to be more resistant than a Ni/La/zeolite reference catalyst, reported in a previous study [40]. The catalyst presents an initial activity around 57 % and selectivity close to 100 %. Feeding water, however, induces a significant decay in the overall activity which decreases to 48 % (by adding 7.4 % H₂O), 39 % (14.8 % H₂O) and 29 % (20 % H₂O). To a lesser extent, the selectivity towards CH₄ formation also tends to decrease; but its maximum loss

Fig. 8. Catalytic performance of the reduced $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}$ catalysts in terms of (a) CO_2 conversion and (b) selectivity towards CH_4 and CO versus reaction temperature. The experiments were performed under a WHSV of $30,000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of 16 % $\text{CO}_2/64 \text{ \%H}_2/20 \text{ \%N}_2$.

Fig. 9. Comparison of light-off temperature (T_{50}) measured over $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}-(5)$ grafted catalyst with those reported in the literature over supported Ni catalysts.

does not exceed 5 %. Notably, upon removing water from the feed gas, the catalyst rapidly recovers its initial activity during the following 40 h, pointing out that the activity loss observed under wet conditions is rather a reversible process. A similar behavior was observed by Quindimil et al. [52] in their previous study on a bimetallic $\text{Ni-Ru}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, tested in the presence of water. They explained the loss of activity to strong chemisorption of water molecules on the active sites. The characterization of the spent sample reveals that there are no significant changes in its textural and structural properties, assessed by BET and XRD techniques, respectively.

Conclusions

In order to improve the performance of a previously reported Ni/HAP impregnated catalyst in the CO_2 methanation reaction, a novel synthesis approach, based on grafting method, is carried out for Ni deposition.

The conditions have been optimized for the grafting of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ complex on HAP support, in a toluene solution. The optimal temperature for a high grafting yield, with an upper limit close to 4.6 % Ni ($9.6 \text{ Ni at. nm}^{-2}$), is found to be $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This result is explained by the simultaneous presence of two types of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ complex adsorption sites, available for (i) physisorption and (ii) chemisorption, respectively. However, increasing the anchoring temperature ($40\text{--}75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) provokes the disappearance of the physisorption sites, since the complex is preferentially attached to the HAP surface via a strong chemisorption. Furthermore, DRS data point out that while physisorbed $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ derived species comprise tetrahedral Ni^{2+} sites, the chemisorption of $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2$ complex mainly leads to a dominant phase composed of octahedrally coordinated Ni^{2+} species.

H_2 -TPR data reveal the presence of three forms of oxidized Ni species in the grafted samples calcined at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: (i) easily reducible Ni_2O_3 , (ii) surface NiO phase and (iii) NiO exhibiting a strong interaction with HAP support. Moreover, XRD and XPS techniques evidence that the activation of the grafted samples at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ induces a complete reduction of Ni species. Due to the interaction metal-support, this activation procedure provokes the occurrence of Ni lattice imperfections resulting from a compressive strain effect. According to HAADF data, the average sizes estimated on the activated Ni grafted catalysts ($3.2\text{--}6.3 \text{ nm}$) are significantly smaller than those measured on Ni/HAP impregnated sample (13.9 nm), reported in our previous studies.

The activated $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}$ grafted catalysts demonstrated a promising performance in the CO_2 methanation reaction, shedding light on their suitability and competitiveness when compared with reference materials prepared by impregnation method. The optimized $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}-(5)$ sample exhibits a T_{50} value close to $313 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and its maximum conversion (84 %) can be achieved at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The high activity of this novel series of active materials is associated with the used grafting method and the role of the HAP support in providing suitable structural and chemical properties. In concrete, there is a clear correlation between the specific activity (TOF) and the relative abundance of easily reducible Ni species as well as the most reactive basic sites. Water addition temporarily reduces the activity of the optimized catalyst; however, this effect is reversible since the activity is fully restored upon water removal. Work is in progress to enhance performance under realistic conditions through the addition of promoters.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nassima Berroug: Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Miguel A. Gutiérrez-Ortiz:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Juan R. González-Velasco:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Zouhair Boukha:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Fig. 10. (a) Variation of TOF_{CH_4} versus the reaction temperature, (b) Arrhenius plots for the reduced $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}$ catalysts, and dependence of TOF_{CH_4} , estimated at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$, on (c) the basic sites, reactive at $T > 500$ $^\circ\text{C}$ and (d) the amounts of α reducible species. The kinetic experiments were performed under differential reactor conditions and a feed composition of $16\% \text{CO}_2/64\% \text{H}_2/20\% \text{N}_2$.

Fig. 11. Stability test for the $\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2/\text{HAP}(5)$ catalyst: (a) CO_2 conversion and selectivity towards CH_4 and CO versus time on stream and (b) zoom in the time interval of 58–72 h to illustrate the effect of water addition (7.4–20%). The experiment was performed under a WHSV of $30,000 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a feed composition of $16\% \text{CO}_2/64\% \text{H}_2/20\% \text{N}_2$.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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